

USMON NASIR'S LIFE AND WORKS AS WELL AS IDEOLOGICAL-ARTISTIC ANALYSIS OF HIS POEMS

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ABSTRACT

In this article, the analysis of artistic arts used in the works of the artist born in Namangan, who sang folk songs, allusions to the writer's skill, thoughts on the epics "Norbota" and "Nakhshon" are highlighted.

KEY WORDS: "Norbota", "Nakhshon", "Heart", "What I said to Nasim", "Night of almond blossoms".

Usman Nasir, who has created a wonderful garden in the blessed and holy place of poetry, is a dew that has not yet flowed from the fountain of great and eternal poetry. They are alive, lively, untouchable pieces of life like eyes.

The coolness of prayer fell on the gardens,

And the flowers turned their leaves,

And the sun drank water,

And the red grass like tulips faded from the mountains below.

Such lines define the overall poetic appearance and poetic tone of the artist. Even when he was labeled as "Enemy of the People" and imprisoned with his great courage, patriotism, and unique talent, he never stopped his enthusiastic action. He firmly believed that he was absolutely innocent in front of the country. Brave, ardent Usman Nasir wrote a petition in the name of Stalin on August 2, 1940. Even while he was in prison, he wrote "Poetic Novel", 3 plays, many reports that he wrote poems "I am still young, full of enthusiasm! "I have to create for the welfare of my people, I am innocent," he said. He was a brave poet who submitted an application to the

"Sultan of the Sultanate". Unfortunately, when the acquittal was announced against him, the poet had filled his eternal life in this world.

Yes, indeed, the poet is still alive today, as if he is walking among us. Already, his works are being read, his poems are being memorized, books and plays are being created about him, all of which once again proves how valid the above verses are. It would be an exaggeration to say that the novel "Usman Nasir" by the talented poet Tora Mirza, the book "Usman Nasir" by the young and sharp writer Jovlon Jovliyev, and the play of the same name have rediscovered him in the imagination of the young generation. not Also, it is necessary to include such works in school textbooks and through this to form the feelings of pride and pride in the hearts of our dear children towards the past and our great ancestors, to create Osman Nasirs of today and the future, and at the same time also relevant. In this regard, especially the decision of our president "On wide celebration of the 110th anniversary of the birth of Atashin poet, translator and dramatist Osman Nasir" is his unique, unfading and sincere way of life, unrepeatable talent, poetic poetry. It is also true that it was an important document that allowed to perpetuate the memory of the great artist who conquered the hearts of millions with his works and to introduce him once again to today's readers!

According to the candidate of philological sciences, associate professor O'tkir Rashid, "The poet is still living. He lives in his beloved garden, in the language of his beloved mother." According to the subject, content, character and nature of Usman Nasir's poems, the literary critic Ibrahim Ghafurov calls Usman Nasir "The wayfarer". "He likes to shoot," he says. This is true. The poet walks like a traveler and road user, taking pictures of the people, events, and the beauty of nature he sees on the roads through poetry. In addition to lyrics, the artist is the author of the dramas "Norbota", "Nakhshon", "Atlas", "The Last Day", "Zafar", "Dushman".

*I looked, my eyes were filled with tears.
A girl with a shadow on her eyelash chest.
I caught my eyes,
My heart was full of blood.*

At this point, the verses of the poet Muhammad Yusuf "From the long eyelashes..." come to our mind involuntarily.

In fact, Usman Nasir became a manly child of the people with his pure and cheerful poetry, poems and epics that shed light on the reality of his time. The poet begins a poem with the following lines:

Oh, how charming she is!

I will drink all their flowers full of light.

The bright spring in my heart is full of light...

How sweet and incomparable verses at the same time!

Isn't this a picture of the garden of the poet's heart?! It's as if his heart is saturated with the light of spring. Ibrahim Gafurov recalls this: "Lighting from within is a very rare phenomenon. Humanity rarely has children. I have observed the radiating of the word from the inside as a miracle in Boborahim Mashrab, Mirzo Ghalib, Heine, Lorca, Cholpon, Usman Nasir.

In conclusion, we should say that the original children of our nation, like Usman Nasir, will never be forgotten. Times change, generations change, but the poem written by the poet, in the lines of his impressive works, in his spirit and melodies, his eternal example shines!

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